

Ticketing System

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III. Description

The Ticketing System is help-line of contact for all those query-requestors who need help for their problem. The ticketing tool has request module which functions as the Help-line manager where all the requests are fetched from the users having query related to their specific problem and then necessary solutions are provided to all those query-requestors by giving them the pre-defined solutions. If there is no solution predefined by the admin then the request for that query is passed on to the technician to resolve the issue.

IV. Proposed architecture

The two primary focal points of the Manage Engine Service Desk Plus are IT Request Tracking and Asset Management. Utilizing the modules of Service Desk, professionals and framework overseers can resolve issues of complex nature in the blink of an eye and along these lines diminish the end-client dissatisfaction emerging because of tedious issue settling process. They can likewise monitor the necessities of the association with the assistance of advantage the board and proactively distribute assets to the correct client/offices, in this way expanding the profitability of the association ServiceDesk has a unified archive that stores applicable data pretty much all the huge elements in your IT condition. The elements, named as Configuration Items (CIs) comprises of Hardware, the introduced Software Applications, Documents, Business Services and People that are a piece of your IT framework.

ABSTRACT

Ticketing system is an IT service management platform. The ticketing tool provides solutions to all clients who are connected with one or more organizations remotely/within the infrastructure. The Ticketing System is also used as a help desk software that can help customer to get their service as efficiently as possible while maintaining their service requests. The platform of ticketing system is deployed in virtual machine which thus can be accessed by anyone within the organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The ticketing tool provides solutions to all clients who are connected with one or more organizations remotely/within the infrastructure. The System is more often used for users who may need help and guide them using pre-defined solutions. The Ticketing System is deployed in cloud virtual machine using AWS environment. The Ticketing tool plays a vital role in IT management sector by solving queries for all end-users.

II. Problem Definition

Most often the new users in the IT Company need help to understand the new system which has been established to learn it. Here the ticketing system can help them by taking those query request, then processing it to give the required solutions. Thus, the ticketing system can become the help-line for all those query requestors and can save the organization from certain financial losses.

Figure 1

V. FLOW DIAGRAM

Figure-2

A. Flowchart Explanation

1. The picture in Figure-01 is the stream graph of the planned how ticket created in oversee motor. Above are the means required from begin as far as possible as clarified in the working area of this content.
2. The various help work area tickets brought up in your association are sorted out and followed in the Requests module. The Requests module empowers you to deal with tickets quickly, dole out tickets to professionals, blend comparative demands, etc. By monitoring the exceptional and past due solicitations, the Request module improves the reaction time and goals time.

VI. Limitations

Each Project is can't be immaculate in unsurpassed, in this manner this undertaking may likewise require future upgradation to show signs of improvement form of itself and beat all the constraint. Which may include:

- By updating the Service Desk, we can include new highlights that assistance improve client's assistance work area execution and upgrade IT administration conveyance.
- We can likewise include Manage Engine Service Desk Plus Mobile Client that can improves the effectiveness and profitability of client help work area framework by furnishing specialists with the capacity to in a flash access their solicitations while they are far from their work area through their cell phones.
- With each arrival of up gradation, existing bugs can be fixed, subsequently lessening the quantity of issues or breakdowns client involvement with Service Desk Plus.

VII. conclusion

Thusly it tends to be inferred that the task is performed by seeing all modules of it. The achievability and prerequisites for these modules are checked. It has been discovered that every one of these modules can be executed all around proficiently and on account of that clients have simple access to their information with secure confirmation. Existing business, programming information, demands, and arrangements can be found between any client and administrator with Service Desk. The framework lets administrator include and screen different administrations like worker subtleties, arrangement subtleties, ticket age, reports. The framework has rich and simple to utilize easy to understand interface that has less expectation to absorb information

VIII. References

- [1]. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5475278>
- [2]. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/6038089>
- [3]. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5475278>